
A STUDY ON CONSUMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF WHITE GOODS ACCORDING TO GENERATION Y AND IGEN

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Abstract:

Purpose

This paper aims to explore purchase intension of consumers towards a white good according to generation Y and igen generation

Design/methodology/approach

This study is based on primary data. Questionnaire is used for the purpose of data collection. The data collected from 500 respondents Chi Square test is used to test the hypothesis. For this study, Dependent variable is purchase intension of Consumers Y and Igen generation and independent variable is mode of purchase (offline and online).

Findings

Consumers of Y generation prefer to buy white goods offline and Consumers of igen generation prefer to buy online goods.

Research limitations/implications

Gen Igen is the newest generation to enter the workforce. With limited research on this cohort, this study synthesized the existing knowledge of IGen generation of consumers towards their purchase intention pf white goods. In this work, the authors provided

organizations and practitioners guidelines to be prepared with Igen generation expectations of consumers towards white goods.

Originality/value

The study is original from nature.

Keywords: Y Generation, iGen, White Goods, Buying Behaviour, Mode of Purchase.

Introduction:

The existence of technology has caused rapid and radical changes in the 21st century while the development and rapid changes of technology have been interacting mutually. These changes have formed the basis of new technologies. These changes experienced have brought about the people, who were born in different periods of time, to have different personalities, viewpoints and values. The changes occurred in economy, culture and politics influence the perception, expectation and viewpoints of the individuals deeply. As a result of these interactions, the borders of period of generations are marked off and their characteristics are determined. Alexis de Tocqueville, a French political thinker and historian, stated in his article called Democracy in America he wrote in 1945 that the United States of America underwent a perpetual change. He referred to the generational turnover as one of the main sources of this change while he was mentioning about aforementioned change. Each young generation, who replaces the old generation, comes along with its own characteristic feature and value judgment (Bennett & Rademacher, 1997). Their different general point of view may change the social and political landscape. The generations, who travel together in the course of time being affected from the same events, have been examined throughout the history in order to understand the psychology of the individuals and keep their behaviour under control. The main reasons why so many researches carried out on the generations today are that the drastic influences of the changes experienced on the individuals can be observed more clearly and “the four generations that have four different characteristics work together” for the first time in the history as the specific period for each generation has been shortened due to the changes underwent. Understanding the generation phenomenon and its chronological difference as well as the traits of the members of generations is of importance as these four different generations that have different characteristics which are separated from one another sharply coexist.

The classification to be used in this study will be the one to be particularly based on the opinions of the experts and evaluation of the historical events though it is likely to observe a lot of different classifications when the international and national literature is reviewed. Generation Name Chronological Generation Classification

- Traditionalists 1900 - 1945
- Baby Boomers 1946 - 1964
- Generation X 1965 - 1979

- Generation Y 1980 - 1994
- Generation Z 1997 - 2012

Literature review

Children and teenagers in the modern media and communication technology. The modern child lives in a highly-dynamic world. Thanks to the free flow of information, they can learn about various events, contact with unlimited number of people, become a member of the information society. The virtual world is attractive and far from reality. In such a network community one can overcome alienation, loneliness and isolation. The attractiveness of this new reality may lead to the situation that online world becomes the main one (Andrzejewska, 2012, pp. 44–46). However, there are also serious threats. Many of them result from a lack of knowledge about the media that should be systematically passed down to children, even in pre-school age. In this sense, one can speak of low media awareness among children and young people. Research carried out by M. Wrońska among children and young people, as well as their teachers, showed that the level of media awareness (it consists of: media knowledge, level of media literacy and attitudes towards the media) can be described as mediocre. At the same time, teachers in these studies fared worse than students. This means a big dissonance between the expectations of young people to the usage of modern technologies in school and education system (Wrońska, 2015, pp. 37–45). One of the most serious threats is related to the loss of privacy in the Internet, which young people are most exposed to. Information posted by them, on the web, often begins to live its own life. Removing it, when is already placed in the cloud, is basically impossible. In addition, many portals apply the rule "use services for data". In practice, if you want to get complete information, you should first answer a number of questions or give an access to personal data, that may reveal a lot of sensitive data (Czopek, 2016, p. 69).

Objectives of the study

- To study about the consumers of Generation Y and Igen generation in India.
- To study the purchase intension of consumers towards offline or online white goods according to Y generation and Igen generation.

Hypothesis of the study

H₀: There is no significant association between purchase intension of Y generation and igen generation according to mode of purchase.

H₁: There is significant association between purchase intension of Y generation and igen generation according to mode of purchase.

Research methodology

This study is based on primary data. Questionnaire is used for the purpose of data collection. The data collected from 500 respondents Chi Square test is used to test the hypothesis. For this study, Dependent variable is purchase intension of Consumers Y and Igen generation and independent variable is mode of purchase (offline and online).

Data analysis

Demographic Profiling of the Sampled Consumers:

Facets		Groups	Percentage
Age	Generation Z	18-21 Years	36%
		22-25 Years	16%
	Generation Y	26-29 Years	33%
		30-33 Years	15%
Gender		Male	53%
		Female	47%
Educational Qualification		Graduation and Below	56%
		Above Graduation	44%
Occupation		Employed	35%
		Self-Employed	33%
		Unemployed	32%
Annual Household Income		Less than 5 Lakhs	32%
		5 to 10 Lakhs	34%
		Above 10 Lakhs	34%
Marital Status		Single	54%
		Married	46%
Family Type		Joint Family	31%
		Nuclear Family	69%

The below table shows the purchase intention of Y generation and igen generation according to mode of purchase:

Intended Mode of Purchase	Mode	Generation		Total	Chi-Square
		Generation Y	iGen generation		
		Offline	121		
Online	126	157	283	6.205**	
Total	247	253	500		

*Note: statistically significant at 5 per cent level of significance

Total data of 500 consumers. Results are statistically significant at 5 per cent level of significant and this shows that mode of purchase differs significantly across the generation.

Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.

Thus, there is significant difference between purchase intension of Y generation and igen generation according to mode of purchase.

Conclusions of the study

It is observed that, out of the total number of consumers, who prefer to buy white goods offline, more number of consumers belong to generation Y. From the total of 217 consumers, who are intended to buy white goods offline line, 121 consumers belong to generation Y in comparison with 96 consumers who intended to buy white goods online and belongs to iGen.

Likewise, out of the total of 283 consumers who are found to shop white goods online, 157 consumers are belong to iGen and 126 are found to belong to the generation Y. This apparently shows that more number of consumers belonging to iGen prefer to buy white goods through online platform, while comparatively more number of consumers, belonging to generation Y, prefer to buy white goods through offline mode.

This study concludes that retailers need to focus on creating a strong online presence as well to target iGen consumers. Additionally, retailers should focus on promoting a wide range of options and easy payment methods can help retailers attract younger customers.

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